

Networked Universal Awareness: a Note

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In this note, the authors propose a view of the universe as a network of masses with gravitational waves as the interaction modality. The question is raised as to what and how does this 'network' universe (NU) compute, or, which problem does it attempt to solve? A possibility is proposed: its own awareness, or the problem of consciousness. The question becomes: why would the NU need a self-awareness? In response, it is suggested that self-awareness is an advantage rather than a relic of the primordial universe.

The proposal can be taken along the following direction. Since the classical action is related to a certain extremal path adopted by a particle in a gravitational field, this extremization problem seems to be the one being computed or solved by the NU, albeit on a massive scale. Our proposal here possibly banks close to that of Seth Lloyd, who views the universe as a quantum computer. Computations are inseparable from brain function and brain function from awareness in neuroscience. Taking the cue that computation and awareness go hand in hand, we might consider this computation to be concomitant with an underlying awareness.

The advantage of this proposal is that on this view, if we then reconsider nervous systems as *generators* of conscious awareness, we can adopt the position that since nervous systems are *within* the NU, their paths and trajectories are already being computed and evolved by the NU. Therefore, we eliminate the chicken-egg issue of whether consciousness came first or nervous systems, and can rest in the view that this computation is self-awareness itself. In other words, we are conflating total knowledge - knowing the full trajectory of every particle - with universal self-awareness. This is not such a novel perspective, having been suggested in the Veda itself¹.

¹*prajnanam brahma*: conscious knowledge is universal awareness.